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Membrane Injury Index and Yield Performance of Maize under Non-irrigated Water Stress

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. Author UKR performed the statistical analysis and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author SS designed the experiment, wrote the protocol and revised the manuscript. Author MMB coordinated and revised the manuscript. Author SKP was involved in determining the membrane injury index, performed statistical analysis and contributed to write and revise the manuscript. Author MSR managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted with four maize varieties (BARI hybrid maize-7, Golden Star, KC 505 and Fortune Gold) to investigate the effect of non-irrigated water stress on membrane injury and yield performance in order to select comparatively drought tolerant maize variety. The experiment was carried out during December, 2015 to May, 2016 at research field of Department of Crop Physiology and Ecology, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Dinajpur, Bangladesh. Comparatively drought tolerant varieties showed less membrane disturbance under water stress. Non-irrigated water stress reduced yield components (total number of cobs plant⁻¹, number of fertile cobs plant⁻¹, seed number cob⁻¹, single cob weight and 100-seed weight) and grain yield in all varieties. In respect to yield and yield components, two varieties (BARI hybrid maize-7 and Golden Star) showed lower reduction than the other two varieties (KC 505 and Fortune Gold) under water stress condition. BARI hybrid maize-7 was found as comparatively drought tolerant,

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whereas Fortune Gold was found as drought susceptible regarding membrane disturbance and yield performance. However, the order of drought susceptibility based on grain yield was Fortune Gold > KC 505 > Golden Star > BARI hybrid maize-7.

Keywords: Maize; water stress; membrane injury index; yield; stress susceptibility index.

1. INTRODUCTION

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the most important cereal grains grown worldwide in a wider range of environments because of its greater adaptability [1]. It is grown mainly for grain but also for fodder. Comparison showed that wheat is cultivated on more area relative to other cereals but yield and production of maize is more than wheat and rice [2]. In Asian tropics, maize is largely (about 80%) grown as rain-fed crop [3]. Uneven distribution patterns of monsoon rain occasionally cause drought at different crop growth stage(s), which is responsible for year-to-year fluctuation in production of rainfed maize in Asian tropics [4]. In Bangladesh, maize ranks third in respect of total acreage after rice and wheat but ranks first in respect of average yield, 2.87 t/ha [5]. In winter a large amount of land remains fallow due to either lack of irrigation facilities or higher prices of irrigation water. Drought stress is seriously affecting the maize crop resultantly hindering the productivity like other crops [6]. Being drought sensitive crop, maize is affected at each and every stage of growth and development by lesser moisture availability [7]. While drought negatively affects all stages of maize growth and production, the reproductive stage particularly between flowering, tassel emergence and early grain filling is the most sensitive to drought stress [8]. Drought stress results in several changes in the subjected plants, including leaf relative water content, electrolytes leakage of plasma membrane, soluble protein content, photosynthetic pigments, carotenoids etc., which in turn decrease the photosynthesis efficiency and photo-assimilate production and finally reduction of crop yield [9]. In this circumstances screening of drought tolerant maize variety(s) might be an effective way to expand maize cultivation and to assure sustainable maize yield under drought prone area. Therefore, the study was conducted to identify the relatively drought tolerant maize variety(s) based on responses of some significant traits to water deficit stress condition.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Location and Duration

The experiment was conducted at the research field and Laboratory of Department of Crop Physiology and Ecology, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Dinajpur during the period of December 2015 to May 2016. The experimental field is located at 25°39' N latitude and 88°41' E longitude with an elevation of 37.58 m above the sea level and under the Agro-ecological zone Old Himalayan Piedmont Plain (AEZ-1). The experimental field is a medium high land belonging to the non-calcareous dark gray floodplain soil with sandy loam texture. The experimental field is under subtropical climate characterized by rainfall during the month of last April to October and scanty rainfall during December.

2.2 Experimental Design and Treatments

The experiment was laid out in a split plot design with three replications. The unit plot size was 3 m×2 m having a plot to plot and block to block distance of 0.75 and 1 m, respectively. The two growing conditions: A) well water condition (irrigation was given at 8-10 leaf stage, silking stage and grain filling stage) and B) water stress condition (no irrigation) were placed in main plots as main plot treatments, whereas four varieties of maize (BARI hybrid maize-7, Golden Star, KC 505 and Fortune Gold) were placed randomly in the sub plots. After sowing slight irrigation was given for uniform germination and other intercultural operations were done as per requirement. The stressed plots were protected from rainfall by rainout shelter.

2.3 Determination of Soil Moisture Content

The soil samples were collected by an augur from each plot at the depth of 15 cm and were taken in air tight containers. The samples were weighed and then dried in an oven at 70°C for 72 hours. The samples were then taken out from

oven and weighed again. The loss in weight (Wt.) was the amount of soil moisture.

Soil moisture content (%) = {(Wt. of moist sample - Wt. of oven dry sample) / Wt. of oven dry sample} × 100

2.4 Determination of Membrane Injury Index

For determining membrane injury index, seeds of four maize varieties were sown in poly bag (12 cm diameter and 20 cm height) filled with a combined medium of soil and compost (weight ratio = 3:1). Two growing conditions (control and PEG induced water deficit) were developed by normal water and dissolving calculating amount of PEG (151.5 g/1000 ml) in tap water as described by Michel [10]. The poly bags were irrigated with required amount of respective solution when necessary. Membrane injury index, I (%) was estimated according to Kocheva et al. [11] using the formula-

$$I (\%) = [1 - (1 - D_1/D_2) / (1 - C_1/C_2)] \times 100$$

Where, D_1 and D_2 represent the conductivity of treated samples after 24 h of incubation and after tissue killing, respectively and C_1 and C_2 are the corresponding values for the control.

2.5 Data Recorded on Yield and Yield Components

Number of cobs plant⁻¹ and number of fertile cobs plant⁻¹ were taken and recorded properly at maturity stage. Single cob weight, seeds cob⁻¹, 100-seed weight and grain yield (t/ha) were recorded properly at harvest time. Grain yield was adjusted to 12% moisture by sun drying and using a moisture meter.

2.6 Calculation of Stress Susceptibility Index

Stress susceptibility index was calculated for grain yield as described by Fisher and Maurer [12].

$$\text{Stress susceptibility index} = (1 - Y/Y_P) / (1 - X/X_P)$$

Where,

Y = Grain yield of variety in a stress environment
 Y_P = Grain yield of variety in a stress-free environment

X = Mean Y of all varieties

X_P = Mean Y_P of all varieties

2.7 Statistical Analysis

The data were analyzed by partitioning the total variance with the help of computer using MSTAT-C program and the treatment means were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range test (DMRT) at 5% level of significance.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Soil Moisture Content

Fig. 1 shows that at seedling emergence stage, there was less variation in soil moisture between two growing conditions (52.16% under well water and 48.23% under water stress). But at tasseling stage there was much variation between well water condition (23.51%) and water stress condition (12.25%). These variations were increasing towards later stages. Finally, at harvest time soil moisture of well water condition was 10.54%, whereas under non-irrigated water stress condition it was 3.22%. The results represent that with the advancement of time after sowing, soil moisture of water stressed plot was reduced gradually. This variation might be due to variation in the rate of evapotranspiration and consumption of water by plants. Payero et al. [13] stated that, effect of timing of a deficit-irrigation allocation resulted in no crop stress during the vegetative period and stress during the reproductive stages, which affected evapotranspiration, dry matter, yield and water use efficiency.

3.2 Membrane Injury Index

Fig. 2 shows that among the four varieties the Fortune Gold showed the highest injury (4.34%) in membrane which indicates disturbance in membrane permeability expressed by greater amounts of electrolyte leakage. BARI hybrid maize-7 had the lowest membrane injury (1.58%) suggesting the less pronounced membrane damages. Golden Star and KC 505 showed moderate disturbance (2.85% and 3.13%, respectively) in membrane. The lowest value of injury index is an indicator of possible stress-induced impairment of membrane permeability which indicates the degree of ion leakage from damaged tissue [14]. Moreover, the lowest injury index value of BARI hybrid maize-7 might be corresponded with the highest stress-induced proline levels. However, based on membrane

injury index BARI hybrid maize-7 might be considered as drought tolerant, whereas, variety Fortune Gold was considered as drought susceptible. Other two varieties viz. KC 505 and Golden Star were moderately drought tolerant.

Results observed by Goodarzian-Ghahfarokhi et al. [15] support the results of the present study. They also found that water deficit stress caused less disturbance in membrane in tolerant variety than the susceptible variety of maize.

Fig. 1. Soil moisture content (0-15 cm depth) at different growing stage as influenced by water regimes. Vertical bars indicate the standard error (±)

Fig. 2. Membrane injury index of four maize varieties under water stress condition. Vertical bars indicate the standard error (±)

3.3 Number of Cobs Plant⁻¹

Number of cobs plant⁻¹ of maize was not significantly influenced by the interaction effect of variety and growing condition but significantly influenced by the main effect (Table 1). Under well water condition, BARI hybrid maize-7 had the highest number of cobs plant⁻¹ (2.10) followed by Golden Star (1.98) and Fortune Gold (1.96). Lowest number was given by the variety KC 505 (1.90). Under non-irrigated water stress condition, all the varieties showed reduction in the total number of cobs plant⁻¹. But the reduction was lowest in BARI hybrid maize-7 (15.23%) and highest in KC 505 (25.10%). The reduction percentage was 16.67% in Golden Star and 20.10% in Fortune Gold. Under stress condition, again BARI hybrid maize-7 had the highest cob number plant⁻¹ (1.78) followed by Golden Star (1.65). The variety KC 505 had the lowest number of cobs plant⁻¹ (1.46) which was statistically at par with Fortune Gold. Ghooshchi et al. [16] and Khoshvaghti et al. [17] also observed reduced cob number plant⁻¹ in maize under water deficit stress condition.

3.4 Number of Fertile Cobs Plant⁻¹

Interaction effect of variety and growing condition was statistically significant on number of fertile cobs plant⁻¹ of maize (Table 1). Under well water condition, BARI hybrid maize-7 produced the maximum number of fertile cobs plant⁻¹ (1.87) followed by Golden Star (1.45), whereas KC 505 and Fortune Gold produced lower cob numbers 1.36 and 1.30, respectively. Non-irrigated water stress reduced the number of fertile cobs plant⁻¹ in all varieties in different magnitude. The reduction was lower in BARI hybrid maize-7 and Golden Star (15.50 and 16.56%, respectively) than KC 505 and Fortune Gold (19.12 and 19.23%, respectively). Under water stress, BARI hybrid maize-7 produced the maximum number of fertile cobs plant⁻¹ (1.58), whereas Fortune Gold produced the minimum number of fertile cobs plant⁻¹ (1.05) which was statistically at par with KC 505. The results of the present study are in agreement with the results reported by Ghooshchi et al. [16] and Sikder et al. [18].

3.5 Single Cob Weight

Single cob weight of maize was significantly influenced by the interaction effect of variety and growing condition (Table 2). Under well water, BARI hybrid maize-7 had the maximum cob weight (259.69 g) followed by Golden Star

(249.89 g) which was statistically at par with KC 505 (246.77 g), while the Fortune Gold had the minimum single cob weight (244.67 g). Non-irrigated water stress reduced single cob weight for all varieties compared to well water condition. The reduction was minimum in BARI hybrid maize-7 (6.13%) followed by Golden Star (9.01%) and KC 505 (9.90%), while Fortune Gold had the maximum reduction (14.64%). Under water stress, again BARI hybrid maize-7 attained the highest single cob weight (243.76 g), whereas Fortune Gold had the lowest single cob weight (213.439 g). This is in agreement with former reports of Sikder et al. [18], Moradi et al. [19] and Meskelu et al. [20] that support the results of the present study.

3.6 Number of Seeds Cob⁻¹

The interaction effect of variety and growing condition on number of seeds cob⁻¹ was statistically significant (Table 2). BARI hybrid maize-7 had the highest number of seeds cob⁻¹ (556.33) followed by Golden Star (520.67) which was statistically at par with other two varieties KC 505 and Fortune Gold under well water condition. Under non-irrigated water stress condition, all the varieties showed reduction in their number of seeds cob⁻¹ at different degrees. The reduction was lower in BARI hybrid maize-7 (10.78%) followed by Golden Star (13.25%) and KC 505 (15.00%) and Fortune Gold had the highest reduction in the number of seeds cob⁻¹ (17.34%). However, BARI hybrid maize-7 again attained the highest number of seeds cob⁻¹ (496.33), whereas the variety Fortune Gold had the lowest number of seeds cob⁻¹ (422.67) under water stress condition. Moradi et al. [19] also stated that the number of seeds cob⁻¹ was reduced significantly under water stress condition which supports the findings of the present study. Similar statement about maize under water stress was also made by Koliai et al. [21] and Hesamoddin et al. [22].

3.7 100-Seed Weight

100-seed weight of maize was significantly varied by the interaction effect of maize variety and growing condition (Table 3). Under well water condition, BARI hybrid maize-7 had the maximum 100-seed weight (30.36 g) followed by Golden Star (27.46 g), whereas Fortune Gold had the minimum 100-seed weight (22.67 g). 100-seed weight was reduced in all varieties due to non-irrigated water stress but the degree of reduction was not same for all varieties. Water

stress reduced the 100-seed weight by 9.62% in BARI hybrid maize-7, 13.26% in Golden Star, 15.81% in KC 505 and 18.53% in Fortune Gold. Under water stress condition, again BARI hybrid maize-7 attained the highest 100-seed weight (27.44 g), whereas Fortune Gold had the lowest 100-seed weight (18.47 g). Results from other studies like Hesamoddin et al. [22] and Khalili et al. [23] also showed that 100-seed weight was significantly reduced due to water stress in maize.

3.8 Grain Yield

Grain yield of maize was significantly influenced by the interaction effect of variety and growing conditions (Table 3). At well water condition BARI hybrid maize-7 produced the highest grain yield (7.63 t/ha) followed by Golden Star (6.84 t/ha) and KC 505 (6.65 t/ha), whereas Fortune Gold produced the lowest grain yield (5.83 t/ha). Non-irrigated water stress reduced grain yield in all varieties in different magnitude. Water stress

reduced grain yield by 9.44% in BARI hybrid maize-7, 13.45% in Golden Star, 14.73% in KC 505 and 16.81% in Fortune Gold. However, under water stress BARI hybrid maize-7 produced the highest yield (6.91 t/ha), whereas Fortune Gold produced the lowest grain yield (4.85 t/ha). Vafa et al. [24] and Sabagh et al. [25] also found that grain yield was significantly reduced by water stress and their results support the results of the present study.

3.9 Stress Susceptibility Index

Stress susceptibility index of different maize varieties based on grain yield (Fig. 3) shows that BARI hybrid maize-7 had the lowest stress susceptibility index value (0.70), whereas Fortune Gold had the highest stress susceptibility index value (1.25). Golden Star and KC 505 showed moderate stress susceptibility index (1.00 and 1.10, respectively).

Table 1. Number of cobs plant⁻¹ and number of fertile cobs plant⁻¹ of maize variety as influenced by well water and water stress

Maize varieties	Water regimes	Number of cobs plant ⁻¹		Number of fertile cobs plant ⁻¹	
		Number	% reduction over well water	Number	% reduction over well water
BARI hybrid maize-7	Well water	2.10	15.23	1.87a	15.50
	Water stress	1.78		1.58b	
Golden Star	Well water	1.98	16.67	1.45c	16.56
	Water stress	1.65		1.21e	
KC 505	Well water	1.90	25.10	1.36cd	19.12
	Water stress	1.46		1.10f	
Fortune Gold	Well water	1.96	20.10	1.30d	19.23
	Water stress	1.47		1.05f	
Level of significance		NS	-	0.01	-
CV (%)		4.40		4.47	

In a column, means having similar letter(s) did not differ significantly by DMRT at 5% probability level

Table 2. Single cob weight and number of seeds cob⁻¹ of maize variety as influenced by well water and water stress

Maize varieties	Water regimes	Single cob weight		Number of seeds cob ⁻¹	
		g	% reduction over well water	Number	% reduction over well water
BARI hybrid maize-7	Well water	259.69a	6.13	556.33a	10.78
	Water stress	243.76abc		496.33abc	
Golden Star	Well water	249.89ab	9.01	520.67ab	13.25
	Water stress	227.38bcd		485.00bc	
KC 505	Well water	246.77ab	9.90	515.67ab	15.00
	Water stress	222.32cd		438.33cd	
Fortune Gold	Well water	244.67abc	14.64	511.33ab	17.34
	Water stress	213.43d		422.67d	
Level of significance		0.05	-	0.01	-
CV (%)		5.26		5.95	

In a column, means having similar letter(s) did not differ significantly by DMRT at 5% probability level

Table 3. 100-seed weight and grain yield of maize variety as influenced by well water and water stress

Maize varieties	Water regimes	100-seed weight		Grain yield	
		g	% reduction over well water	t/ha	% reduction over well water
BARI hybrid maize-7	Well water	30.36a	9.62	7.63a	9.44
	Water stress	27.44b		6.91b	
Golden Star	Well water	27.46b	13.26	6.84b	13.45
	Water stress	23.82cd		5.92d	
KC 505	Well water	25.43bc	15.81	6.65c	14.73
	Water stress	21.41d		5.67e	
Fortune Gold	Well water	22.67d	18.52	5.83d	16.81
	Water stress	18.47e		4.85f	
Level of significance		0.01	-	0.05	-
CV (%)		5.73		3.26	

In a column, means having similar letter(s) did not differ significantly by DMRT at 5% probability level

Fig. 3. Stress susceptibility index of four maize varieties based on grain yield

4. CONCLUSIONS

Tolerant varieties showed greater membrane stability under water deficit stress. In response to membrane injury index and yield performance, BARI hybrid maize-7 was found as comparatively drought tolerant and Fortune Gold was found as drought susceptible, whereas the Golden Star and KC 505 varieties were found as moderately drought tolerant. The order of stress susceptibility regarding grain yield was, Fortune Gold > KC 505 > Golden Star > BARI hybrid maize-7.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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